

Studies on the Beans of *Spatholobus roxburghii* Benth.

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Spatholobus roxburghii, belonging to Leguminosae family, is widely distributed in the plains from the foot of the Western Himalayas to Ceylon and is used extensively as a remedy in dropsy, worms and in snake poisons¹. Jones² reported the presence of rotenone in one per cent yield in the root. We have undertaken the studies on the beans of *S. roxburghii* as it was not chemically examined before. The investigation revealed the presence of a fatty matter, friedelin and β -sitosterol. The homogeneity of the compounds were confirmed by thin layer chromatography.

The powdered beans of *Spatholobus roxburghii* (700 gm) was successively soxhleted with petroleum ether (60–80°), benzene and methanol. The concentrated petrol extract was kept in ice-chamber when a white waxy solid separated (800 mg), m.p. 81–82°. It could not be worked further. The mother liquor after the separation of the above compound was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The petrol ether eluates gave a waxy solid, m.p. 82°, besides large quantities of oil; the benzene eluates of the chromatogram gave a solid, m.p. 242–47° (200 mg) which responded to the Libermann-Burchard test for triterpenes. Several crystallisations of this solid from petrol gave friedelin, m.p. and mixed m.p. 257–59°, $[\alpha]_D^{30}$ –28.1° (CHCl₃) [Found : C, 84.05; H, 11.62; Calculated for C₃₀H₅₀O : C, 84.50; H, 11.74%]. [Lit.^{3,4} m.p. 260–62°, $[\alpha]_D$ –29°], Identity was confirmed by comparison of I.R. and N.M.R. spectra with those of an authentic sample of friedelin, isolated in our laboratory from *Raupellia grata*⁵.

The benzene extract of the defatted plant material was concentrated and chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The benzene eluate gave β -sitosterol, m.p. and mixed m.p. 132°, $[\alpha]_D$ –35°, acetate, m.p. 126°.

The methanolic extract of the plant material was worked up for the isolation of basic materials when neither any crystalline solid could be isolated nor any tests for alkaloid could be obtained.

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